

1 **PBX1 silencing in treatment-resistant HER2+ breast cancer.**

2 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
3 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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8 1. We studied whole tumor gene expression in humans with pathologic complete response (pCR) or residual
9 disease (RD) following treatment for HER2+ breast cancer to discover gene expression changes associated with,
10 resulting from or causing resistance to treatment with the HER2-targeted treatment trastuzumab (Herceptin).

11 2. We identified activation of the homeobox transcription factor PBX1 in humans whose tumors display
12 resistance to treatment with trastuzumab.

13 3. Studying whole transcription in HER2+ breast cancer cells engineered to develop trastuzumab-resistance *in*
14 *vitro* validated this phenomena.

15 4. Thus, we discovered PBX1 activation follows or supports resistance to trastuzumab in humans with HER2+
16 breast cancer, and are the first laboratory to do so.

17 5. Subtype-specific treatment of breast cancer has begun but remains limited: in luminal A and luminal B breast
18 cancers, cancers that are hormone receptor positive (HR+), this includes use of endocrine therapies to target ESR1
19 expression.

20 6. In HER2+ breast cancers, subtype-specific treatment of disease includes the use of agents trastuzumab,
21 pertuzumab and neratinib, immunoglobulin- and small molecule-based inhibitors of HER2; targeted therapies in triple
22 negative (ESR- PGR- HER2-) breast cancer are non-existent.

23 7. Understanding of resistance to treatment of breast cancer and other solid tumors, cancers that affect humans
24 today, also remains limited.

25 8. To understand the molecular mechanism underlying resistance to HER2-targeted therapy in humans with
26 HER2+ breast cancer, we studied whole transcription in the tumor following treatment with trastuzumab in a small
27 cohort of humans with HER2+ breast cancer, stratified based on treatment response - pathologic complete response,
28 or pCR, versus those with residual disease (RD), which we considered treatment resistance given the fact that HER2+
breast cancer is defined by HER2+ positivity and trastuzumab is a monoclonal antibody recognizing HER2.

9. The document here provides basic, translational and clinical evidence for silencing of PBX1 in
treatment-resistant HER2+ breast cancer:

i. The patient has failed trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer.

ii. This patient will likely progress to metastasis.

1. 50% of patients with HER2+ breast cancer develop metastasis to the CNS (brain).

iii. This patient will likely progress to CNS metastasis.

iv. CNS metastasis frequently results in death.

10. The silencing agent is under development.

Figure 1: PBX1 activation is a signature gene expression change associated with trastuzumab resistance.

GSE20194

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer (pCR)

n=2 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer with residual disease (RD)

Probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
212148_at	0.00056512	-5.2061985	0.16102	-1.6614	PBX1	116/22283	99.5

Figure 2: Biological significance of PBX1 activation as a reflection of trastuzumab resistance is validated by study of whole transcription in cultured breast cancer cells engineered to develop trastuzumab resistance *in vitro* by clonal selection in Herceptin.

GSE15043

n=2 BT474 cultured breast cancer cells

n=8 BT474 clones with engineered trastuzumab resistance, selected in 0.2uM or 1uM Herceptin

Probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
205253_at	1.63e-03-4.02	-0.978977	-2.93e-01		PBX1	660/54675	98.8

PBX1 activation was among the gene expression changes most evident, across the entire transcriptome of HER2+ tumors and breast cancer cells in culture, following artificial induction of (Figure 2) or naturally occurring resistance to trastuzumab (Figure 1).

We discovered a likely functional role for PBX1 in driving resistance by studying human survival in a large cohort of humans with HER2+ cancer (*n*=695 patients) (Figure 3). Time to recurrence was 162.58 months for HER2+ patients with low PBX1 tumor expression, while it was 126 months for HER2+ patients with high tumor expression of PBX1.

Figure 3: In HER2+ but not basal subtype breast cancer (*n*=953 patients), increased PBX1 activation correlates with time to recurrence (relapse).

Caption: Kaplan-Meier survival data from HER2+ patients is shown here (left), along with basal subtype patients (right).

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11. We demonstrated here for the first time *PBX1* activation in resistance to trastuzumab in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.

12. We are currently studying the function of homeobox transcription factors including *PBX1* in transformation and the transcriptional program of the solid tumor.

13. It is likely that *PBX1* is one of a group of genes whose function is to support trastuzumab resistance *in vivo*.

14. It is likely *PBX1* induction is a primary and fundamental event governing resistance in HER2+ breast cancer.

15. It is likely that effective, controlled (temporally) *PBX1* silencing will induce tumor regression in patients with treatment resistant HER2+ breast cancer who have failed treatment with trastuzumab.

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Methods

We studied whole transcriptome tumor gene expression using published microarray data from a small cohort of humans ($n=4$) treated with trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer. We studied whole transcriptome gene expression data from cultured breast cancer cells ($n=2$ BT474 versus $n=8$ BT47 with $n=4$ separate clones and $n=2$ each) to support the biological significance of our findings that PBX1 activation is a *bona fide* signature gene expression change of the trastuzumab resistance program. R-based computational methods were utilized to study and measure changes in gene expression globally. Patients also received neoadjuvant chemotherapy which included 5-fluorouracil, cyclophosphamide, paclitaxel, and doxorubicin.